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D8.2: Project Communication Report

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Deliverable Review and Approval

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

	Key Event	Deadline	Done by
1	Submission of Draft Deliverable to reviewers	<i>Tues 5 Nov 2019</i> <i>(180 days after the officially foreseen submission date in the DoA)</i>	Francesc Rodriguez
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3	Uploading and submission of Final Deliverable on Participant Portal	<i>Fri 29 Nov 2019</i> <i>(150 days after the officially foreseen submission date in the DoA)</i>	Francesc Rodríguez
4	Review	<i>27/05/2020</i>	Alexander Gerber & Chiara Iurlaro

Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to outline the internal and external communicative framework of Project Ô. It constitutes a first necessary stage towards the Project Communication Strategy (D8.3), which is to be delivered in month 18. The present deliverable includes an internal and external communication analysis of the consortium, the key communication objectives based on a segmentation of target audiences in three clusters, and the key messages and means of communication employed.

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1. Introduction

Project Ô is a European Commission Innovation Action (Horizon 2020 program) coordinated by IRIS srl (Italy), started in June 2018 and lasting four years. The main aims of the project are to implement innovative “small water loops” in four demonstration sites, and to assess their efficacy and efficiency to achieve reduction of energy cost, to treat water pollutants in new ways, and to improve the quality of used water, among other specific goals. Project Ô is based on the project's successful implementation in four demonstrations sites in Italy, Israel, Spain, and Croatia. Throughout the duration of the project, communication plays a pivotal role, and thus, it must be planned, structured and organised in a way that supports its objectives.

Just to put this report into context, it is necessary to consider that the European Commission Decision of 2014 (4995) states that “activities to disseminate information and exploit research and innovation results as well as carry out communication activities will be an important and integral part of Horizon 2020”. Similarly, the Article 38 of the model grant agreement prescribes that “the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner” (AGA, 2018).

Effective Communication in general and an upstream stakeholder engagement in particular are high priorities in Project Ô. Workpackage 8 (WP8) is facilitating this by diverse means of communication and formative evaluation of its impacts. The Deliverable 8.2 (D8.2) is based on, but goes beyond, the components of the communication plan described in the Description of Action (part B, pp.62-63). D8.2 is an analysis of expectations and capacities for communication within and beyond the project consortium, and has to be considered as a practical tool to facilitate the development of the Communication Strategy (D8.3), which will be delivered in month 18.

It is important, thus, to distinguish between this Communication Report (D8.2) and the Communication Strategy (D8.3). Whereas the Communication Report is an analysis of the current and potential tools for the internal and external communication of the project, the Communication Strategy sets the direction for all of the communication plans, according to the needs of stakeholders in each demonstration site.

Having this in mind, it is important to highlight that communication is not a goal per se, but a means for all beneficiaries of the consortium to help fulfil the objectives of the project plan. Through communication, the project has the capacity to form opinions, engage stakeholders in the development of the project, understand and discuss ideas and attitudes about water, co-create knowledge in the demonstration sites, raise awareness, understand the position of stakeholders in a dynamic environment, etc.

This document provides practical support for project internal and external communication. It should be seen as a practical tool to provide communication among the project beneficiaries and between the project and other stakeholders. This document should be also regarded as adaptable and measurable, building on the strengths and needs of the project consortium beneficiaries and external stakeholders.

2. Situation analysis

2.1 Internal and external communication

The internal communication is key for working effectively at all levels and for project engagement. The internal communication has been established since the first day of the project and maintained throughout its course through several channels (see section 6.1 in this report).

The external communication refers to communication established with external stakeholders of various types. Project Ô has started to communicate at the beginning of the project (see Milestone 30 report), and in doing so, the project has created a distinguishable brand identity mainly based on its logo and name, as it is shown below.

2.2 Project name and logo

The name of Project Ô was chosen because Ô is pronounced as EAU (water, in French) and is written as a circle, reminding of the circularity of water reuse.

Another important action to establish the identity of the project is the design of a logo that has been used in the documentation and communicative material of the project.

The logo was made by the Project Ô beneficiary Heim.art, who were inspired by a sphere, which represents water as the basic element of life.

Water is also the basic element of movement and human interaction. The issue of water is and will be increasingly critical on the whole planet Earth. The logo of the Project Ô represents the circular nature, the movement, and the essence of water as an element. In dealing with the development of water management systems, Project Ô aims not only to improve systems for purifying water, but also to purify the relationship between humans and water, relying on technology, but also local histories and social structures. Different communities have different relationships to water, they relate to it in a different way and approach it in a different way. However, regardless of the shade of emotions related to water, for everyone the notion of water is a clear, blue flow.¹

The idea behind the two shades of blue and white lines is to describe the variety of three 3 stages of water (solid, liquid and gas), two main types of water occurring in nature (fresh and salt water), and water before and after being treated. The flow between these types is what Project Ô is interested in.

Lighter shade of blue	RGB/CMYK R: 20 B:153 G: 205 / C: 77% M: 25% Y: 4% K: 0%
Darker shade of blue	RGB/CMYK R: 2 B: 102 G: 153 / C: 93% M: 58% Y: 18% K: 2%

2.3 Analysis of expectations and capacities for communication within the consortium²

A project internal online survey was conducted in June 2019 to determine the communication expectations and capacities within the consortium. The survey was distributed twice electronically on June the 13th 2019, and on August the 7th 2019.

¹ Information provided by Heim.art

² It has to be updated with new respondents in late August.

In total, this survey was answered by 29 representatives of 21 project beneficiaries. This means that most of the beneficiaries (institutions) of the consortium (91,3%) have responded to the survey (n = 21, N = 23).

Based on this survey, several internal lists have been created, containing:

- The names and contacts of the public relations officers of 15 project beneficiaries.
- 16 Twitter accounts associated with Project Ô's beneficiaries (including both personal and company/department accounts), which, in total, have 96,332 followers (in October 2019).³
- 11 known LinkedIn accounts associated with Project Ô's beneficiaries.
- Facebook accounts of 10 beneficiaries.
- 42 relevant communication channels⁴ to communicate about Project Ô provided by 18 of the beneficiaries.
- 21 related projects (about water management, circular economy, etc.) with contact details of their representatives, who are likely to create synergies with Project Ô.

Regarding the internal project communication, 91% of the respondents (n = 20) feel sufficiently informed to conduct the tasks for their work packages in order to accomplish the goals of Project Ô. 9% (n = 2) of those who responded this question said that they do not feel well enough informed to conduct their tasks (the rest do not know or do not answer).

Ease of finding information:

When asked about the ease of finding information about Project Ô, most survey respondents agree (45%) or strongly agree (35%) that it is easy to find it on the minutes of the conference calls. 15% of those participating in the survey are neutral to this statement, and 5% disagree with it.

50% (n = 11) agree, and 18% strongly agree that it is easy to find information through the mailing lists (18% being neutral about such claim, and 14% against it).

29% of the respondents agree (n = 5) or strongly agree (24%) that it is easy to find information through the social media accounts of Project Ô. 41% are neutral to it.

41% of the respondents agree (n = 9) and 36% strongly agree that it is easy to find information through the website. 9% disagree with it.

30% of the respondents agree (n = 6) and 20% strongly agree that it is easy to find information about the project through the internal newsletter. 35% are neutral to it. 10% disagree and 5% strongly disagree with it.

Lastly, 38% of respondents are neutral (and 25% disagree and 13% agree), when asked about the easiness to find information through the Sciebo cloud service. One fourth of them strongly agrees that it is easy to find information about the project through Sciebo.⁵

Future use of communication tools:

³ This includes a variety of institutional Twitter accounts with very different number of followers. The expectation is that the project will make use of this resource at certain times to announce important achievements.

⁴ This involves sustainability magazines, environmental and university events, among other potential communication channels/activities, which could be used for any communicative purpose.

⁵ In addition, one beneficiary has claimed to find information through the Description of Action and another by getting in direct contact with partners, when needed.

When asked about how our beneficiaries want to receive information concerning the development of Project Ô in the future, most of respondents agree (35%) (n = 7) or strongly agree (40%) that they want to use the minutes. Most of them agree (38%) (n = 8) or strongly agree (38%) that they would get information through mailing list, and 39% agree (n = 7) and 17% strongly agree want to receive information through Project Ô's social media channels. Almost 9 out of 10 of the respondents, agree (30%) (n = 6) or strongly agree (60%) that they would like to get access to information through the website. Finally, most of the surveyed beneficiaries agree (45%) (n = 9) or strongly agree (40%) that internal newsletters and the Sciebo cloud service (38% strongly agree and 19% agree) should be sources of information about Project Ô.

A fourth of the surveyed members consider that the online edition of documents is "not at all important" to develop their work for the consortium. Almost half of the surveyed beneficiaries (45%), on the other hand, consider that simultaneously editing an online document, instead of doing this separately, is "important" for developing their work. For almost a third of the respondents, this function is "slightly important".

In your view, which objectives should Project Ô meet? Explain why (see Appendix 2)

This open question allowed any kind of answer. Water is clearly the main word that appears in the data set. The main objectives are related to environmental protection, economic opportunities, and the regulatory development that the project has to offer. In general, though, respondents mention a set of objectives, which are equivalent to the objectives expressed in the Description of the Action. For example, these objectives involve the demonstration of water reuse and the multi-user collaborative platforms. In some cases, the project objectives are formulated using an own narrative identity, characterised by a plain style, which is easy to understand. For example, one respondent said:

Project Ô should demonstrate that you should look no further than your neighborhood to get your water, to minimise impacts and ensure you are using just the right type of water you need (stop using drinking standards water to cool down metals or laser sources or wash plants producing paints, detergents, clothes etc). The correct tools should be put into place: a set of technologies that can be applied flexibly and have a low environmental impact overall and low impact (or positive) on the local people and environment; a set of regulations and tariffing which helps the users to implement this approach; a way of understanding what the direct and indirect savings can be (e.g. recovery of surfactants or cosmetic components from plant washes). This should translate in lower treatment costs and impacts (energy use, chemical use etc) than current technologies.

Which message(s) do you expect Project Ô to convey to the different publics through Project Ô's communication channels? (see Appendix 2)

The main messages that respondents want to pass are linked to the impact of Project Ô, followed by the need to communicate about the results of the project, and finally, how the project is undertaken. Thus, the messages that the respondents expect from the project are about its impact (mainly economic but also environmental and societal), results and process of development.

Given your role within the consortium, what contribution do you see yourself making to the overall success of Project Ô? (see Appendix 2)

As expected, respondents provide with a variety of answers, which cover a range of roles and disciplines. This is a demonstration of the transdisciplinary nature of the project, and how this transdisciplinary orientation is distributed among the different beneficiaries to achieve the different goals and to create positive impacts on the environment and society.

As stated in the Description of Action, the three main objectives of Project Ô are:

- Objective 1. To demonstrate a novel distributed water network that enable the use of alternative sources of water, such as brackish/salt water, collected rainwater, own/external wastewater.
- Objective 2. To demonstrate a Multi-user Collaborative Platform allowing water systems authorities, regulators, and water users to evaluate the overall effects of introducing and regulating small water management loops.
- Objective 3. To demonstrate integrated and participative approaches to water planning that involve directly the community, integrating social science research throughout the entire innovation process.

When asked about the importance of these objectives, the respondents answered the following:

	Low priority	Medium priority	High priority
Objective 1 →			100% (n = 21)
Objective 2 →		25% (n = 5)	75% (n = 15)
Objective 3 →		38% (n = 8)	62% (n = 13)

The more technical the goal is to be achieved by the project, the more it is seen as a high priority by the respondents. This can be interpreted as a sign of the importance that the new modules and technologies have in the development of the project. Although important, the other aspects of the project, like regulatory and social aspects, are seen as supplementary to the technological side of the project.

Project Ô will organise public events in the demo-sites. How much do you disagree or agree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
During the event, the participants of the demo-sites should learn from watching, listening and viewing material produced by Project Ô.			24%	52%	24%
During the event, the participants of the demo-sites should be able to ask questions to our technical partners in an interactive way.				52%	48%
The event should have a consultation process consisting in sharing views and knowledge among stakeholders of the demonstration sites and between these stakeholders and our partners.		5%	20%	50%	25%

The event should lead to an open deliberation process with other stakeholders of the demonstration sites, and group problem solving together with our partners.		5%	33%	43%	19%
The event should facilitate the co-creation of knowledge between stakeholders of the demo-sites and the partners of the consortium in order to include such knowledge in decision-making of Project Ô.		5%	10%	62%	24%

The above statements have been placed in order from less to more engagement with stakeholders. In general, most of the respondents either agree or strongly agree with these statements. An implication of this is the possibility that the communication/engagement events include processes, which combine a comprehensive range of possibilities in terms of communication goals.

The second statement, which says, “during the event, the participants of the demo-sites should be able to ask questions to our technical partners in an interactive way”, provides the highest “strongly agreed” percent response. This is way of communication that creates an opportunity for stakeholders in the demonstration sites to clarify any doubts about the development of the project.

Project Ô will produce communication material for local authorities and the local population in the demo-sites. How much do you disagree or agree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The communication material should enhance the visibility of Project Ô.			4%	48%	48%
The communication material should focus on the specific solutions of the technologies provided by the consortium.			9%	67%	24%
The communication material should deal with regulatory and political aspects of water.		10%	33%	57%	

The communication material should enhance recognition and value of circular water systems.			5%	38%	57%
The communication material should explain and quantify risks connected to circular water systems and water reuse.		10%	14%	43%	33%
Given that public perception of water reuse is a limiting factor in its expansion, the communication material should show advantages of water reuse and tackle its stigma.			10%	25%	65%

Regarding the communication material in the demonstration sites, most of the respondents either “agree” or “strongly agree” with the content of it. Nevertheless, the two aspects that most responders emphasize is the need to communicate first about the advantages of water reuse in order to tackle its potential stigma, and second, about the value of circular water systems.

The Communication Strategy (D8.3) will take the analysis of these results into account.

3. Project Ô and communication objectives

In this section of the deliverable, the project objectives (“What does Project Ô want to achieve?”) and the communication objectives (“What does Project Ô want to accomplish by implementing this communication plan?”) are going to be presented and linked to each other.

3.1 Project Ô objectives

As formulated in the Description of the Action, the overall objectives of Project Ô is to successfully implement novel water distribution systems in four demonstration sites. In doing so, the project delivers:

- innovative water treatment technologies and control systems, which can be deployed flexibly to process difficult pollutants (dyes, pesticides, pharmaceuticals) and when needed because of modularity, mobility and low operational costs.
- interfacing decision making platforms that allow regulators and adopters to achieve consensus over the introduction of a certain localised water management loop, considering both circular economy drivers and protection of the interests of a territory and its population.
- an overall consultative and participatory approach to the decision making over the water management choices, from technology to water resource use planning, to manage stakeholders expectations and achieve acceptability among the majority of water users.

3.2 Communication objectives

Project Ô has communicated publicly since the start of the project in June 2018. We have followed general communication guidelines by the European Commission (see e.g. Appendix 1).

Project communication in Project Ô aims at serving as a transdisciplinary link to inform the implementation and to some extent even specification of circular water systems in the four demo-sites. This can only be accomplished by understanding the needs and expectations, issues and concerns of different stakeholder groups.

4. Key audiences for communication and segmented objectives

4.1 Key audiences

Project Ô is an Innovation Action of the HORIZON 2020 Program, and as such, three main clusters of target audiences have been identified, which include a series of organisations, institutions, projects, initiatives, and other types of stakeholders. The below list goes from general to specific, but it has not been created in any particular order, and especially not in an order of importance.

Cluster I – European Commission agencies and institutions
Policy and decision makers and influencers within the European Commission in relation to areas of interest for Project Ô (Circular Economy, Environment, Sustainable Development Goals, etc.)

Cluster II – Circular Water Sector and related projects to Project Ô
Sister projects related to Project Ô and the broader circular water sector in research and industry, also including the EU-funded ICT4WATER cluster projects

Cluster III – Demonstration sites (see D8.1)			
Italy	Israel	Spain	Croatia
Several stakeholders in relation to alternative water sources for drinkable water supply.	Several stakeholders in relation to reused water for aquaculture and agriculture.	Several stakeholders in relation to reused water for agriculture and urban water uses.	Several stakeholders in relation to reused water for a textile company.

This list will be re-evaluated as Project Ô progresses.

4.2 Communication objectives based on segmented audiences

Given the different communication targets, the communication goals are divided into nine objectives (Cluster I and Cluster II) plus the specific cases of the demonstration sites, which will require specific communication strategies. For communication purposes, it is important to highlight that these eight objectives sometimes overlap and are not mutually exclusive. For example, by encouraging other sister projects (Level II) to know Project Ô’s best practices,⁶ the project can also contribute to showing the degree of scientific excellence and the European added value in the water sector (Cluster I).

Cluster I (EU agencies and institutions) ⁷	Cluster II (Circular Water Sector and related projects to Project Ô)	Cluster III (Demonstration sites)
To show that research solves societal and environmental challenges in Europe (and Israel)	To raise the awareness and increase the understanding of how Project Ô relates to other similar projects (e.g. ICT4Water projects)	Multidirectional communication with stakeholders and engagement activities ⁸
To show scientific excellence and European added value in the water sector	To encourage others to know about and follow our best practices	
To show that research (by Project Ô) promotes European competitiveness and the circular economy	To build trust and reputation for Project Ô’s modules and technologies as game changers in the water sector	
To highlight the transnational aspects of H2020 projects	To articulate a joint vision of a new infrastructure wave in the water sector based on “small loops” and the circular economy	
Challenges and opportunities of regulatory change in circular economy of water at the European level		

⁶ A best practice can be defined as the techniques, methodologies, technologies, procedures or participatory processes that were implemented and improved the project as it developed. For the analysis, existing KPIs will be taken into account.

⁷ For more information, see: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

⁸ This is a first approximation and serves only to highlight the general way that communication objectives will be articulated in the demonstration sites. The communication in the demonstration sites will ultimately depend on the perceptions and needs of stakeholders in Italy, Israel, Spain and Croatia.

5. Messages

5.1 Key messages⁹

These are key messages that set the context for communication management and provides the foundations for communicating with different stakeholders in the Clusters I and II.

Cluster I (EU agencies and institutions)	Cluster II (Circular Water Sector and related projects to Project Ô)	Cluster III (Demonstration sites)
Project Ô is a transnational cooperation in a European (and Israeli) consortium	Increase awareness and understanding of how Project Ô relates to other similar projects (e.g. ICT4Water projects)	Using different languages, key messages will be used to reach target audiences in each demonstration site. The key messages will revolve around the acceptability and attitude towards risk in relation to use (or reuse) of alternative water sources.
Project Ô drives scientific excellence in the water sector in Europe and elsewhere and it may anticipate regulatory changes	Project Ô implements real-life techniques, methodologies, technologies, procedures or participatory processes which are successful and have an impact in specific contexts of application	
Project Ô contributes to European competitiveness and is part of new infrastructure wave necessary for circular economy business models	Project Ô modules and technologies are game-changers and change makers.	
Project Ô solves societal and environmental challenges in Europe (and Israel) through (not only) innovative technologies (eg. impact on everyday lives, contribution to SDGs, climate change, etc.).	Project Ô is part of a series of efforts to rethink current water distribution systems.	
Project Ô implements real-life techniques, methodologies, technologies, procedures or participatory processes which are successful and have an impact in specific contexts of application Project Ô reliable for policy advice.		

⁹ These key messages will be potentially reshaped during the course of the project.

6. Means of communication

6.1 Internal communication

To facilitate internal communication, the project (WP1 and WP8) has facilitated internal communication channels:

Item	Responsible
Conference calls	IRIS srl
E-Collaboration ¹⁰	HSRW
Templates for deliverables, milestones and presentations	IRIS srl
Internal Newsletter	HSRW
Password-protected area on the website	HSRW
Face-to-face meetings (e.g. General Assembly)	Rotatory

6.2 External communication

The external communication channels are the following:

Item	Responsible
Website	HSRW
Social Media	HSRW & an Editorial Team
Twitter, Facebook and Instagram	HSRW
LinkedIn community of practice	HSRW
Youtube	HSRW
Communication materials in form of print-flyers and brochures	HSRW
Public Engagement Activities	To be included in the Project Communication Strategy D8.3 deliverable

¹⁰ Sciebo is particularly safe because the data is stored in Germany (Europe). The data “provider” (in GDPR terms) is the Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Münster (Münster University).

- Website (see MS30 and D8.5)

The Project Ô website was publicly launched in September 2018 after two weeks of testing prior to the launch. The name for the website was chosen by voting by the Work Package leaders. In the end, the name chosen was WWW.EU-PROJECT-O.EU. The website is hosted and maintained by the Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences partner in Germany, and it is backed up and updated regularly (see Deliverable D8.3).

- Social Media Editorial Team

Given the transdisciplinary nature of Project Ô, the subject-matter expertise is dispersed throughout the consortium beneficiaries, and this requires some kind of coordination to communicate about the different aspects of the project. An editorial team, thus, is necessary for meeting the demands of finding and delivering great content about Project Ô's innovative technologies, the circular economy of water, the implementation of technologies, and the problems that Project Ô's technologies solve in each demo-site, among other topics. Through a rotatory social media editorial team, Project Ô will represent a broader range of subject matter in relation to Project Ô (see Appendix 2).

- Twitter, Facebook and Instagram (see MS30)

Twitter is the preferred social media channel in EU-funded projects (EC, 2018, p. 7). Project Ô's Twitter account has been the main place to release new information about the project, the demonstration sites, and the events which the project has organised or participated in. The Twitter account of Project Ô has 303 followers until October 2019.

The content of Project Ô's tweets is spread forward through Facebook (25 follows) and Instagram (49 followers) platforms.

- LinkedIn

A community of practice has been created on LinkedIn. Project Ô community of practice is a group of people from different backgrounds who share an interest in water management and the circular economy. The goal of Project Ô's community of practice is to deep our understanding of circular water systems by interacting on an ongoing basis, asking and answering questions, co-creating knowledge, reusing ideas and programmes that have proved successful elsewhere.

- YouTube

A YouTube channel has been established with the expectation that the first video will be released in Fall 2019, containing parts of interviews from consortium members.

- Communication materials in form of print-flyers and brochures

Two brochures have been created and distributed to various occasions (water management conferences, water congress, etc.). For example, the second brochure can be accessed here: <https://hochschule-rhein-waal.sciebo.de/s/uyytsNiTFoBwXPA>

- Public Engagement Activities

They will be included and specified in the D8.3 report.

The external quantitative targets of external communication are (see MS30 report):

	1 year into the project (March 2019)	2 years into the project (March 2020)	3 years into the project (March 2021)	Target (May 2022)
General public¹¹				
Youtube	0	200	300	500 views
Twitter	ca. 60	250	350	500 followers
Facebook	242	600	1200	1000 likes
Technical audience				
LinkedIn	0	50	100	100 followers
Youtube	0	50	100	100 views
Twitter	ca. 240			100 followers
Internal newsletter	70	70	70	50 each issue (average)
External newsletter	10	500	650	500 each issue (average)
Private section of the website	50	50	50	50

¹¹ As defined in the Description of Action.
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7. Conclusions and Next steps

This deliverable, Project Communication Report (D8.2), has shown both the internal and external communication capacity of the Project Ô consortium, and how project and communication objectives are interrelated for specific target groups. These target groups can be divided into three clusters, which each of them require specific communication messages.

Moreover, through an internal survey, it has been identified that the key messages, which the project wants stakeholders to know, are related to the impact that the project intends to have in economic, environmental and societal terms. Given that respondents give the highest priority to the technological aspects of the project, it can be argued that showing the (economic, environmental, and societal) impacts of the technologies is a message that the project wants to deliver. Also, the results and processes of the project are documented as important aspects to communicate.

As previously mentioned, this deliverable is a necessary step towards the Project Communication Strategy (D8.3), which is to be submitted in month 18. The Project Communication Strategy will be informed by this deliverable (D8.2), and the specific needs of the different stakeholders at different levels. The communication strategy will have to take into account its own context of application, as there is no a one-fits-all approach for all stakeholders in communicative terms. This communication strategy will include the action plan and performance of the internal and external communication, and the media context of each demonstration site.

8. Addendum (post-review)

As indicated in the deliverable, Project Ô is expected to increase its efforts in communicating what also the consortium expressed as its highest priority: to emphasise the economic, environmental, and societal implications which the implemented technologies are expected to have.

Deliverable 8.2 was mainly expected to analyse these internal communication needs and the external communication potential, whereas deliverable 8.3 was planned to outline more in detail how these objectives can be expected to be achieved.

Project Ô is happy to confirm that it fully acknowledges the significance of interdisciplinary in how the technologies are planned to be implemented. The diffusion of innovations in the four demo-sites and the potential for a sustainable scalability of the interdisciplinary solutions beyond the project time-line, will be fostered by intensified communication and valorisation efforts that will emphasise the environmental and societal impact of closing water loops with innovative technologies as foreseen in this project.

Appendix 1 – Communication Top Tips

TOP TIPS¹²	COMMUNICATIVE STEPS TO FOLLOW	
THINK, PLAN, AND ACT STRATEGICALLY	What do you want to achieve?	Begin at the beginning – communicate from day one

¹² Based on European Commission, 2016: <https://ec.europa.eu/easme/en/files/toptipsjpg>
Project Ô – GA 776816Deliverable D8.2 - Public (revised)

YOU CAN'T REACH EVERYONE	Choices need to be made	Use consortium resources, expertise & ideas		
THINK ISSUE – NOT PROJECT	What issue is the project addressing or contributing to?	Link communication hot topics in society and/or timely events		
MAKE IT RELEVANT TO EVERYDAY LIFE	So what? – Show the impact on society	Avoid jargon / technical language, use the words you would use if you were speaking to your grandma	Don't overstate your case (you cannot solve the world's challenges on your own)	
BE CREATIVE	Connect with your inner child	Vamp up the visual, reduce the writing	Catch attention with photos, graphs, infographics, animations, and videos	Use social media, winning the social media scene
GET INTO THE MINDSET OF THE MEDIA	Identify relevant media people, get to know them & the way the sector works	Deadlines, embargos, "off the record", understand media language & needs		
THINK GLOBAL – ACT LOCAL	Local and regional media are highly effective targets	Use the project's local connections	A good story will escalate – local, regional, national, and international	
BUILD YOUR BRAND AND REPUTATION	Use the project's credentials to your advantage e.g. awarded EU funding, renowned scientists	Become a trusted source and voice	Contribute where and when you can	

Appendix 2 – Qualitative data survey

Since this is a public deliverable, the qualitative data survey will be included in the confidential deliverable (D8.3) in order to guarantee the anonymity of the responders.

Appendix 3 – Social Media Guidelines

The goal of these guidelines is to make explicit the type of external communication that project beneficiaries will use for a variety of stakeholders. These guidelines offer a roadmap for beneficiaries to know the key audiences for communication, to be aware of communicative objectives and key messages to be used in response to these objectives, and to provide a set of principles about how to communicate in the context of a Horizon 2020 project. Finally, these guidelines offer some instructions so that project beneficiaries can contribute to the task of communication coordinated by HSRW.¹³

Social Media Editorial Team.

- The goal is to draft about 20 Tweets per month (1 Tweet per workday).
- The repo file is reachable through:

<https://hochschule-rhein-waal.sciebo.de/s/J58TQQxqILDrhyv>

password: ~~XXXXX~~

- **Key Messages** (section 3 in this document) are “meta-messages” which have to be specified, for example, through:
 - Dissemination activities and achievements.
 - Meet our team section.
 - Updates from the demonstration sites.
 - Project events.
 - Conferences: Each beneficiary will communicate, one week in advance, to (email of person responsible for communication) about the participation in conferences and similar meetings.
- Etc

The point is to **link the specific actions, info, and so on, with these “meta-messages”** either implicitly or explicitly. Key messages are just a way to focus our creativity on specific themes, but the potential to create specific messages and combine them is endless.

- The official hashtag of the project is **#EUProjectÔ**. In your tweets, you can use also related hashtags (#ICT4WATER, #WaterReuse, #CircularWater, #WaterManagement, #H2020, #CircularEconomy, #EUfunded, #SDGs, #SDG6, #SDG12, #SDG13, #RRI). It is recommended always to capitalize the first letter of each word of hashtags. Please, suggest new hashtags if necessary.

¹³ The original guidelines document provided to beneficiaries include sections 4 and 5 of this deliverable.
Project Ô – GA 776816Deliverable

References

- European Commission, (2014) Commission Implementing Decision of 22.07.2014. Brussels, 22.7.2014 C(2014) 4995 final. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/3/2014/EN/3-2014-4995-EN-F1-1.Pdf>
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